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APPLYING MLOPS IN SOFTWARE QUALITY ASSURANCE OF THE ANALYTICS APPLICATION MARKET

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INTRODUCTION

- MLOps application context refers to the situations and circumstances in which MLOps, or machine learning operations management practices, are applied to ensure effective implementation, maintenance, and improvement of machine learning (ML) systems.
- MLOps is particularly important in environments where a diverse range of ML models are used. This context includes situations where image recognition, natural language processing or regression models are present, with the need to manage their diversity and complexity. In software development, MLOps is applied to integrate ML development with standard software processes. This includes version control, code management, testing and implementation. Situations where it is necessary to quickly adjust models or introduce new iterations require MLOps practices. This is especially useful in areas where data changes frequently or where it is necessary to respond quickly to new requirements. MLOps is crucial in sectors where high standards are set for data security and regulatory compliance.
- Applications with high data volume or variable requirements require an MLOps approach to ensure scalability and efficient resource management. In areas where data is dynamic and requires continuous model education, MLOps is critical to keeping models up-to-date and accurate. Introducing MLOps into these contexts allows organizations to effectively manage the complexity of ML systems, ensure high levels of performance, and adapt more quickly to changes in the environment.

MLOPS CYCLE

The MLOps cycle, or MLOps process, is a continuous sequence of activities implemented to develop, test, implement, and maintain ML models over time.

Identification of the specific problem that the ML model could solve is presented on Figure 1. ML optimization phase involves cleaning, transforming and normalizing the data to make it suitable for creating and training a ML model using prepared data.

Here, different algorithms and parameters are experimented with in order to achieve the best possible accuracy. Evaluation of model performance on separate data sets that were not used during training includes parameter validation and testing to ensure the generalizability of the model.

Integration of the model into the real environment are used to deploy the model into production, including automated processes for updating and rolling back old versions when needed.

Setting up a real-time model performance monitoring system enables the identification of potential problems and performance degradation in anticipation of a negative impact on users.

Continuous optimization of the model is based on new data and experiences. Updating the model to maintain high accuracy and adequately respond to changes in the environment.

The MLOps cycle is a dynamic process that implies continuous attention, adaptability and cooperation between different teams in order to achieve and maintain a high level of performance of ML models in production.

MLOPS CYCLE

ELEMENTS OF MLOPS

Identification of key elements in MLOps, including automation and model performance monitoring, are implementing in all phase of software development life cycle (SDLC). Automation is a fundamental element of MLOps, and its goal is to reduce human intervention and accelerate all stages of development, implementation and maintenance of ML models (Figure 2). There are new opportunities in automation:

- **Continuous integration (CI):** Implementation of CI/CD (Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment) practices enables automatic testing and integration of new code into a shared repository. This ensures a faster flow of the development cycle.
- **Model training:** Creating processes that automatically train models when new data is delivered, while monitoring performance and adjusting models as needed.
- **Deployment:** Automation of the process of deploying the model to the production environment, including dependency management, environment configuration and resource monitoring.
- **Performance testing:** Regular automated testing of model performance to identify problems and ensure constant optimal functioning.

Fig. 2. MLOps combination

INTEGRATING MLOPS IN SDLC

Software development faces a number of challenges, and the integration of MLOps provides the opportunity to solve some of the key problems in this area (Table 1).

	Challenge	MLOps solution
1. Complexity of development processes	Traditional development processes can be complex and inefficient, especially when it comes to implementing ML models.	MLOps enables the automation and standardization of the entire model life cycle, simplifying the processes from model training to its implementation.
2. Lack of coordination between development and operations teams	Lack of collaboration between development and operations teams can lead to problems in implementing	MLOps integration creates a bridge between development and operations.
3. Lack of transparency in the life cycle of the ML model	Lack of clear visibility into the lifecycle of a model can lead to problems in monitoring performance	MLOps provides tools to track all stages of a model's life, from training to implementation, ensuring transparency and change tracking.
4. Difficulties in managing different versions of the ML model	Managing multiple versions of a model can be a challenge, especially when a large number of models need to be updated and maintained.	MLOps enables simple model versioning, supporting easy update, pull, and change tracking.
5. Lack of reproducibility in model training	Lack of reproducibility in the model training process can lead to problems in validation and retraining.	MLOps provides an environment that enables accurate reproducible training of models, thus ensuring consistency and validity of results.

LIFECYCLE PIPELINE FOR AI APPLICATIONS

Integrating MLOps into existing software development processes requires a systematic and careful approach. These steps are the foundation for successful integration, ensuring consistency, transparency and efficiency in the management of ML models.

CASE STUDY: INTEGRATING MLOPS INTO ANALYTICS APPLICATION DEVELOPMENT

There are many software that we can use to integrate into MLOps to make faster SDLC. Here are presented Databricks, Apache Zeppelin, KNIME and RapidMiner as which are frequently used platforms.

- **Databricks** provides a comprehensive ecosystem for data analytics and ML, offering tools for working with large data sets and support for integration with MLOps practices. It provides support for popular ML libraries like Apache Spark MLlib and Scikit-learn. Also, it enables easy training, evaluation and implementation of the model directly in the platform. Databricks supports working with different data sources and formats, and also allows easy integration with various data warehouses, whether they are in the cloud or on-premises.
- **Apache Zeppelin** is another example of a data analytics application that can serve as a foundation for MLOps integration. Zeppelin is an open-source project designed for interactive data analysis, visualization and ML execution. It provides an interactive environment that supports multiple programming languages, including Scala, Python, R, and SQL.
- **KNIME** (Konstanz information miner) analytics platform is another powerful data analysis application that can be used as the basis for MLOps integration. It is an open-source platform with an active community of users. This gives users the opportunity to customize and extend functionality according to specific needs. It provides visual programming, allowing users to construct analytics workflows without having to write code. KNIME enables users to create analytical workflows by connecting visual nodes, facilitating the construction of complex data analysis and ML models without the need for coding.
- **RapidMiner** is an advanced data analysis platform that allows users to easily build analytical models and perform complex data analysis. It is also an active open-source project with a vibrant community of users. This platform can serve as an excellent foundation for MLOps integration, providing support for automation, model performance monitoring, and team collaboration.

IMPLEMENTATION OF MLOPS IN APPLICATION DEVELOPMENT

Implementing MLOps in software development process involves a series of steps that include planning, modeling, testing, implementation, and maintenance. In tables 2, 3, 4 and 5 is a detailed breakdown of the steps involved in implementing MLOps for the example applications we've previously discussed: Databricks, Apache Zeppelin, KNIME Analytics Platform, and RapidMiner. For each application, the tools and techniques that can be used are listed separately.

DATABRICKS PLATFORM

SDLC	Tools	Techniques
Defining MLOps objectives	Databricks Workspace for defining goals and team communication.	Databricks notebooks for collaborative planning.
Model development	Databricks notebooks, Apache Spark MLlib, MLflow for model experimentation, development and monitoring.	Databricks experimental libraries for model optimization and testing. Apache Spark MLlib for ML. MLflow to track experiments, manage models, and log metrics.
Testing	MLflow for automatic tracking of test results and performance evaluation.	Integrating automated tests into the Databricks environment.) Monitoring of test results and evaluations.
Implementation	Jenkins for deployment automation, Databricks API for integration with CI/CD tools	Setting planned tasks for regular model implementation.) Integration with CI/CD tools (eg Jenkins) for continuous delivery.
Maintenance	MLflow for monitoring model performance in production.	Automated model updating via MLflow tools. Automated model updating based on new data

APPACHE ZEPPELIN

SDLC	Tools	Techniques
Planning	Apache Zeppelin for setting goals and defining features for MLOps integration.	Zeppelin notebooks for collaborative team planning.
Model development	Apache Zeppelin notebooks, MLOps platforms like MLflow for tracking experiments.	Zeppelin API to integrate with MLOps tools.
Testing	Zeppelin notebooks for implementing automated tests.	Track test results directly in the Zeppelin environment.
Implementation	Jenkins for deployment automation, Zeppelin API for integration with CI/CD tools.	Setting planned tasks for regular implementation of the model.
Maintenance	MLflow for monitoring model performance.	Periodic model updating and optimization through the Zeppelin environment.

KNIME ANALYTICS PLATFORM

SDLC	Tools	Techniques
Planning	Defining MLOps objectives in the KNIME environment.	Identification of key functionalities for monitoring and managing models.
Model development	Creating analytical workflows for development and experimentation.	Integration with MLOps tools like MLflow to track metrics and experiments.
Testing	Defining model performance tests within KNIME workflow	Automated testing using KNIME analytics nodes.
Implementation	Automation of the implementation process through integration with CI/CD tools.	Using KNIME Server to manage models in production.
Maintenance	Model performance monitoring through KNIME Server and MLOps platforms.	Periodic model updating and optimization.

RAPIDMINER PLATFORM

SDLC	Tools	Techniques
Planning	Setting goals for integrating MLOps into RapidMiner.	Identification of key functionalities for model lifecycle management.
Model development	Using visual programming in RapidMiner Studio to build models.	Integration with MLOps platforms like MLflow for tracking experiments and models.
Testing	Creation and implementation of model performance tests within RapidMiner Studio.	Test automation using RapidMiner Server.
Implementation	Automation of the implementation process through integration with CI/CD tools.	Using RapidMiner Server to manage models in production.
Maintenance	Model performance monitoring through RapidMiner Server and MLOps platforms.	Periodic model updating and optimization.

CONCLUSION

Results of this research confirm that the application of MLOps is of critical importance for the optimization of software quality assurance in the analysis application market. We hope that this case study will serve as a basis for further research and application of MLOps in various industrial contexts, thus contributing to the innovation and advancement of software development worldwide. This case study highlights the key benefits of implementing MLOps, including faster iterations, real-time error detection, and continuous software optimization. Through this integration of tools and practices, we emphasize the importance of continuous evolution and adaptation in order to achieve a competitive advantage in the analytics applications market as Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud and Amazon Web Services.